

**Tensors and Analytic Structure
in Hamiltonian Theory**

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Abstract

A tensor formulation of Hamilton's equations is presented that utilizes an antisymmetric fundamental or metric tensor, a^{ij} , for the Hamiltonian phase space. In tensor form, the differing kernel symbols of the conjugate variables are replaced by a single kernel symbol w^i , with the consequence that the generalized coordinates and the conjugate momenta are distinguished solely by their *contravariant* and *covariant* transformation rules, respectively. The invariance of the contravariant form of Hamilton's equations leads to an alternative definition of the Poisson bracket condition for canonical invariance, while invariance of the covariant form gives the corresponding definition of the Lagrange bracket.

A complex formulation of Hamilton's equations is studied by introducing the complex dynamical variables: $z^k = q^k + ip_k$. The complex form arises naturally by choosing a basis in which the antisymmetric metric of the symplectic formulation is diagonal. In this representation, the complex dynamical variables, z^k and its complex conjugate, $z^{\bar{k}}$ - are incorporated as the eigenvectors for the diagonal (hybrid) representation of a^{ij} - denoted by $a^{i\bar{j}}$. A tensor formulation of the equations is presented by utilizing the hybrid-index notation. The canonical invariance of the Hamilton's equations is then shown to imply the unitary invariance of the complex form.

By considering transformations of a single complex dynamical variable, the Cauchy-Riemann conditions for analyticity are shown to imply the Poisson bracket conditions for canonical invariance. By considering the class of transformations preserving the antisymmetric structure of Hamilton's equations to within a constant, we show that canonical invariance may be regarded as a special case of conformal invariance.

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1. Introduction

In previous work [1], a tensor formulation of Hamilton's equations has been investigated via the introduction of a Riemannian metric [2] into the Hamiltonian phase space. In the Riemannian case, the fundamental tensor, g_{ij} , is the metric of configuration space, i.e. the N -dimensional linear vector space whose points are given by a specific configuration of the N mechanical degrees of freedom or "generalized" coordinates. The metric is symmetric, i.e. $g_{ij} = g_{ji}$, and positive definite with signature $\underbrace{(+, +, \dots, +)}_{N (+)s}$, and is identified through the kinetic energy as the mass matrix [3] for the system. By introducing the Riemannian metric into the Hamiltonian phase space, we may raise and lower indices on the contravariant generalized coordinates, q^i , and the *covariant* conjugate momenta, p_i , to obtain a consistent transformation rule for both dynamical variables.

Following a literal interpretation of the symplectic formulation [4,5,6,7,8] of Hamiltonian mechanics, the goal has been to combine the conjugate variables into a single multiplet quantity: $(q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N, p^1, p^2, \dots, p^N)$, so that Hamilton's equations may be expressed as a single tensor equation. However, a tensor formulation is desirable for other reasons, namely so that we may investigate Hamiltonian invariance using tensor transformation theory. But, as found in this earlier investigation, the introduction of a Riemannian metric destroys the canonical form of Hamilton's equations. In fact, the extra terms reduce the equations to Lagrangian form; so as a consequence of using a Riemannian metric to raise and lower indices, the Hamiltonian structure returns to the Lagrangian case from which it derives. Additional details may be found in [1].

Sections 2 and 3 are provided as background for Section 4. Given that the goal of this work has been to provide a tensor formulation of Hamilton's equations, the tensor form of Lagrange's equations is presented to both set the notation and lay down a framework for the derivation of Hamilton's equations in Section 3. The utility of the Lagrangian formulation is that it gives a simple procedure for obtaining the

dynamical equations of motion in terms of an arbitrarily chosen set of coordinates. When there are constraints involved, the Lagrangian formulation gives a systematic procedure for eliminating the constrained degrees of freedom - given a transformation from Cartesian to the curvilinear generalized coordinates. The basis for such a procedure stems from the invariance of Lagrange's equations under general coordinate transformations in configuration space - a fact that is demonstrated in Section 2 using the tensor notation.

Traditionally, the understanding of this invariance has been based on the observation that Lagrange's equations are precisely the Euler-Lagrange equations originating from a variational principle in configuration space. So we begin Section 2 with a variational derivation of the Euler-Lagrange equations. As another approach to studying this invariance, Hamilton's equations are derived from the Lagrangian case by replacing the generalized velocities by their corresponding conjugate momenta. The study of coordinate transformations in configuration space is then replaced by the study of canonical transformations in phase space. In Section 3, we derive Hamilton's equations and observe the contravariant transformation rule of the generalized velocities, \dot{q}^i , and the naturally occurring covariant transformation rule of the conjugate momenta, p_i . The Poisson bracket conditions for canonical invariance are derived as a consequence of the invariance of Hamilton's equations - providing a basis for the canonical transformation theory discussed in Section 5.

In Section 4, we present Hamilton's equations in tensor form. In the first sub-Section entitled *Symplectic Formulation*, we give a tensor formulation of the traditional symplectic approach to Hamiltonian mechanics. The antisymmetric metric, a^{ij} , is deduced from the structure of Hamilton's equations and is used to raise and lower indices on the conjugate variables to give a contravariant formulation of the equations. To effectively use index notation, we replace the kernel symbols, q and p of the conjugate variables with the symbol w . This has the effect that coordinates and momenta may be distinguished solely by the contravariant/covariant transformation rules, respectively. The purpose of this Section is not so much to emphasize these results, but rather to provide a suitable background for a derivation of the complex form of the equations presented in the following Section.

Given the naturally occurring antisymmetric metric discussed in the previous Section, we present the complex form of Hamilton's equations under the heading: *Unitary Formulation*. The complex form of the equations has been discussed in several places - see for example: Marsden [5] - p. 55, Fetter-Walecka [3] - p. 204, Salutan-Cromer [9] - p. 204, and Goldstein [6] - p. 430. The usual approach has been to combine the coordinates and momenta into a single complex variable: $z^k = \dot{q}^k + i \dot{p}_k$, and then add the corresponding right-hand sides of Hamilton's equations to obtain the complex form. But this seems less than satisfactory (at least from an aesthetic viewpoint) for several reasons, namely:

- (a) there seems to be lacking a clear motivation for combining the variables in this fashion,
- (b) will it be possible to unambiguously label z with a tensor index, i.e. is it z_k or z^k ?
- (c) the complex form results in a single dynamical equation, but in nonlinear cases the real and imaginary parts of the equation will not always separate - giving a coupled system including the complex conjugate of z^k as a dynamical variable. Adding the conjugate variable may be justified by requiring an equation for each unknown, but again there seems to be lacking other motivation for it, especially since the full content of Hamilton's equations is contained in the single equation of the complex form.

(a), (b), (c) are naturally resolved by choosing a basis in which the metric, a^{ij} , is diagonal. In this representation, we find that the eigenvectors (invariant vectors under the raising/lowering operation) of a^{ij} are exactly z^k and $z^{\bar{k}}$ (\equiv complex conjugate of z^k). A tensor formulation of the equations is then presented utilizing the hybrid-index notation due to Schouten [2, 10] - fully equivalent to the *bra-ket* matrix notation invented by Dirac [11] for the purposes of quantum theory.

In Section 5, we study the invariance of Hamilton's equations using transformation theory. Invariance of the symplectic form leads to an analogous result for the Poisson bracket derived in Section 3, but given the tensor form of the equations, we show that the antisymmetric metric may be defined from the Poisson bracket result for canonical invariance. Invariance of the contravariant form of the equations gives the definition of the Poisson bracket, while invariance of the covariant form defines the Lagrange bracket. In the sub-Section entitled *Unitary*, we show that canonical transformations preserving the

symplectic form correspond to the “unitary” invariance of the complex form. The origin of this invariance may be attributed to the hermitian character of $a^{i\bar{j}}$, i.e. the diagonal representation of a^{ij} .

Given the complex dynamical variables arising in the unitary formulation presented in Section 4, it would be interesting if there exists a relation between canonical invariance and *complex analytic* or *holomorphic* structure. As shown in Section 6, such a relation does exist but we shall only consider it for the case of 2-d phase space - leaving the more intricate study of multiple complex variables to a later investigation. In the first part of this Section, we give the preliminary definitions of an analytic function and then give a derivation of the Cauchy-Riemann conditions for analyticity. In the following sub-Section entitled *Conformal Invariance*, a brief discussion is given of the transformation properties of analytic functions - and then in the final sub-Section we show that canonical invariance may be regarded as a special case of conformal invariance. Conformal invariance in the Hamiltonian theory has also been discussed by Kilmister [12] and Lee [13], but from a completely different viewpoint. The results presented here are consistent with these earlier works.

2. Lagrangian Formulation

Newton's laws give differential equations for the trajectory of a mass point moving in 3-dimensional Euclidean space, R_3 , or along a curve or surface embedded in Euclidean space if constraints are present. A system of N masses may be considered by associating a given configuration of the system with a unique point in $3N$ dimensional configuration space. In order to properly introduce constraints, it is convenient to define a coordinate transformation that reduces the number of degrees of freedom to exactly the number of coordinates. In the former case, the coordinates are Cartesian variables, x_n^i , of a centered R_{3N} , while in the latter case the coordinates, q^i , are the generalized coordinates of a V_N . Solving these differential equations gives the time evolution of a system traced by following a point along a trajectory in configuration space.

The Lagrangian formulation of mechanics may be constructed by considering the scalar formed by the Lagrangian function L , having the functional dependence:

$$L(q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N, \dot{q}^1, \dot{q}^2, \dots, \dot{q}^N, t) = T - V, \quad (2.1)$$

where T is the kinetic energy, and V is the potential that we assume to be velocity independent. As we show in the first sub-Section, the equations of motion may be derived from a variational principle [14,15]. In an earlier study [1], we have already given a formulation of Lagrange's equations that emphasize the geometric aspects we wish to bring out here. However, we derive in this section a condensed version of the equations to emphasize the tensor methods, and to show explicitly the invariance of Lagrange's equations under transformations of generalized coordinates.

Euler-Lagrange \equiv Lagrange's Equations

Consider the functional, $J[q^i, \dot{q}^i]$, i.e. the mapping: $J: C^2_{[t_1, t_2]} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defined by the integral

$$J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(q^i(t), \dot{q}^i(t), t) dt, \quad (2.2)$$

where t is taken as a parametrization of a curve in V_n , and C^2 is the space of twice differentiable functions. The Euler-Lagrange equations of motion may be derived as the first order necessary condition (FONC) for (2.2) to be extremal. To clarify, let us assume that q^i gives a local minimum for $J[q^i, \dot{q}^i]$.

We may consider a variation of q^i by a perturbation: $q^i + \delta q^i$, so we take $r \approx \delta q^i$. Since q^i is a local minimum we must have

$$\Delta J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] = J[q^i + \delta q^i, \dot{q}^i + \delta \dot{q}^i] - J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] \geq 0, \quad (2.3)$$

and if we consider δq^i to be small, a Taylor series expansion in δq^i gives (using the Einstein sum convention defined over repeated indices in an upper/lower combination):

$$\Delta J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] = \partial_{q^i} J \delta q^i + \partial_{\dot{q}^i} J \delta \dot{q}^i + \frac{1}{2} \left(\partial_{q^i \dot{q}^i}^2 J \right) \delta q^i \delta \dot{q}^i + \dots,$$

which may be expressed using the variational notation:

$$\Delta J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] = \delta J + \frac{1}{2} \delta^2 J + \frac{1}{3!} \delta^3 J + \dots$$

Now, if δq^i is small enough we may write $\Delta J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] \approx \delta J$, and if we assume for the moment that δq^i is constant then $\delta \dot{q}^i = 0$, and we have $\delta J \geq 0$ from (2.3). If δq^i is negative then $\delta J \leq 0$ which implies that

$$\delta J = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

The relation given in (2.4) is referred to as Hamilton's principle [3]. Assuming that we may differentiate under the integral in (2.2), we obtain the FONC (*weak form*) that J be extremal:

$$\delta J[q^i, \dot{q}^i] = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\partial_{q^i} L \delta q^i + \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \delta \dot{q}^i \right) dt = 0. \quad (2.5)$$

Integrating the above, first notice that (using $d_t \equiv \frac{d}{dt}$):

$$\partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \delta \dot{q}^i = d_t \left(\partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \delta q^i \right) - \delta q^i d_t \left(\partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \right),$$

so (2.5) becomes

$$\delta J = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\partial_{q^i} L - d_t \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \right) \delta q^i dt + \left(\partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \delta q^i \right) \Big|_{t_1}^{t_2} = 0.$$

Assuming the condition of vanishing endpoints, i.e. $\delta q^i(t_1) = \delta q^i(t_2) = 0$, we obtain

$$\delta J = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left(\partial_{q^i} L - d_t \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L \right) \delta q^i dt = 0,$$

but since the δq^i are arbitrary, we must have

$$\partial_{q^i} L - d_t \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L = 0. \quad (2.6)$$

Equation (2.6) gives the Lagrangian equations of motion, i.e. the FONC (*strong* form) that (2.2) be extremal. This condition gives N second order differential equations of motion - equivalent to those obtained from the Newtonian case, but with the important distinction that (2.6) gives a covariant expression of the dynamical equations under transformations of generalized coordinates - as will be demonstrated in the following sub-Section.

In Tensor Form

The metric of configuration space may be obtained from the kinetic energy. Consider a point mass m moving along a trajectory defined by a curve s in configuration space. The Riemannian expression for distance along s is given by

$$ds^2 = g_{ij} dq^i dq^j, \quad (2.7)$$

where g_{ij} is non-singular, symmetric, and positive definite. Equation (2.7) contains two notational devices that will be used extensively. Repeated indices occurring in an upper/lower combination imply summation (Einstein sum convention) while upper and lower indices indicate the contravariant and covariant transformation rules, respectively. Given a transformation of coordinates:

$$q^k \rightarrow q'^i = q'^i(q^j),$$

a contravariant vector A^i is defined by the transformation rule:

$$A'^i = \frac{\partial q'^i}{\partial q^j} A^j, \quad (2.8)$$

while a covariant vector is given by

$$B'_i = \frac{\partial q^j}{\partial q'^i} B_j. \quad (2.9)$$

The definitions in (2.8) and (2.9) are illustrated above for tensors of rank 1 (vectors) but are easily extended to tensors of higher rank.

Writing

$$dq^i = \dot{q}^i dt,$$

(2.7) may be expressed

$$ds^2 = g_{ij} \dot{q}^i \dot{q}^j (dt)^2,$$

giving the velocity of the mass m along s :

$$v^2 = \left(\frac{ds}{dt} \right)^2 = g_{ij} \dot{q}^i \dot{q}^j.$$

By definition, the kinetic energy is

$$T = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \frac{1}{2} m g_{ij} \dot{q}^i \dot{q}^j, \quad (2.10)$$

so in the case of a conservative potential, the Euler-Lagrange equations of motion may be expressed:

$$d_t (\partial_{\dot{q}^i} T) - \partial_{q^i} T = F_i, \quad (2.11)$$

where F_i is the generalized force defined by: $F_i = -\partial_i V(q^k)$. Using (2.10), we calculate each term on the LHS of (2.11):

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_{\dot{q}^i} T &= \frac{1}{2} (g_{ij} \dot{q}^j + g_{ij} \dot{q}^i \delta_j^i) = g_{ij} \dot{q}^j \\ d_t(\partial_{\dot{q}^i} T) &= g_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + \partial_k g_{ij} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j \\ \partial_i T &= \frac{1}{2} \partial_i g_{kj} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j,\end{aligned}\tag{2.12}$$

so (2.11) becomes

$$g_{ij} \ddot{q}^j + \partial_k g_{ij} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j - \frac{1}{2} \partial_i g_{kj} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j = F_i.\tag{2.13}$$

Noting the symmetry over the index combination, jk , on the middle term LHS, we may rewrite it using the mixing operation[†]

$$\partial_{(k} g_{|i|j)} \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_k g_{ji} + \partial_j g_{ki}) \dot{q}^k \dot{q}^j.$$

giving (changing the free index from i to l):

$$\begin{aligned}d_t(\partial_{\dot{q}^i} T) - \partial_{q^i} T &= g_{lj} \ddot{q}^j + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_k g_{jl} + \partial_j g_{kl} - \partial_l g_{jk}) \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k \\ &= g_{lj} \ddot{q}^j + \Gamma_{ljk} \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k,\end{aligned}\tag{2.14}$$

where

$$\Gamma_{ljk} = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_k g_{jl} + \partial_j g_{kl} - \partial_l g_{jk}).$$

Multiplying both sides of (2.14) by g^{il} we get

$$\ddot{q}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^i \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k = -g^{il} \partial_l V = Q^i,\tag{2.15}$$

using the definition of the Christoffel coefficients (see for example Schouten [2] - p. 132):

[†] The mixing operation (see Schouten [2] - p. 14) is defined on p indices by adding $p!$ isomers formed by permuting the indices in all possible ways and then dividing by $p!$. Indices involved in the operation are enclosed by () and indices to be excluded are surrounded with | |.

$$\Gamma_{jk}^i = g^{il} \Gamma_{ljk} = \frac{1}{2} g^{il} (\partial_k g_{jl} + \partial_j g_{kl} - \partial_l g_{jk}). \quad (2.16)$$

If no external forces are acting on the system, we obtain the equations for a geodesic (see Schouten [2] - p. 156) in configuration space:

$$\ddot{q}^i + \Gamma_{jk}^i \dot{q}^j \dot{q}^k = 0. \quad (2.17)$$

If there are constraints present, the Riemann-Christoffel curvature tensor, $R^i_{.jkl}$, defined by

$$R^i_{.jkl} = \partial_k \Gamma_{jl}^i - \partial_l \Gamma_{jk}^i + \Gamma_{mk}^i \Gamma_{jl}^m - \Gamma_{ml}^i \Gamma_{jk}^m \neq 0, \quad (2.18)$$

is not necessarily zero, showing that in general configuration space is not flat. As expressed in (2.15), we have obtained Newton's Second law in tensor (covariant) form. Alternative derivations of these equations have been given elsewhere, most notably by Whittaker [16], McConnell [17], Sokolnikoff [18], Synge-Schild [19], and Havas [20] - where further discussion and additional references may be found.

3. Hamiltonian Formulation

Hamilton's Equations

The Hamiltonian description of mechanics may be derived from a Lagrangian formulation by considering the Lagrangian function, L , having the functional dependence:

$$L = L(q^1, q^2, \dots, q^N; \dot{q}^1, \dot{q}^2, \dots, \dot{q}^N; t), \quad (3.1)$$

and then defining the conjugate momenta:

$$p_i = \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L, \quad (3.2)$$

where the lower index marks the covariant transformation rule under a transformation of generalized coordinates: $q^k \rightarrow Q^i$. The total differential of (3.1) may be written as

$$dL = \partial_i L dq^i + \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L d\dot{q}^i + \partial_t L dt,$$

and then after substituting from (3.2) we get

$$dL = \partial_i L dq^i + p_i d\dot{q}^i + \partial_t L dt. \quad (3.3)$$

Expressing (3.3) in terms of the independent variables q^i and p_i , we make a Legendre transformation

(see Arnold [4] - p. 61) from (q^i, \dot{q}^i, t) to (q^i, p_i, t) by noting that

$$p_i d\dot{q}^i = d(p_i \dot{q}^i) - \dot{q}^i dp_i.$$

Substituting the above into (3.3) have

$$dH = d(p_i \dot{q}^i - L) = \dot{q}^i dp_i - \partial_i L dq^i - \partial_t L dt, \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$H = p_i \dot{q}^i - L, \quad (3.5)$$

defines the Hamiltonian function. From Lagrange's equations we have

$$d_t(\partial_{\dot{q}^i} L) = \partial_i L = \dot{p}_i, \quad (3.6)$$

and if we consider the differential of $H(q^i, p_i)$:

$$dH = \partial_i H dq^i + \partial_{p_i} H dp_i + \partial_t H dt, \quad (3.7)$$

we see by inspection of (3.4), (3.6), and (3.7) that

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}^i &= \partial_{p_i} H \\ \dot{p}_i &= -\partial_{q^i} H, \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\partial_t H = -\partial_t L. \quad (3.9)$$

The first two equations are Hamilton's equations of motion and the last equation shows that if L is not an explicit function of t , then $\partial_t H = 0$, and in this case H is a constant of motion. The upper and lower indices in (3.8) notates the contravariant and covariant tensor transformation rules of the Hamiltonian variables, q^i and p_i , respectively. By convention, an upper index is attached to the q^i although in general, the generalized coordinates do not have a tensor transformation rule. The convention is adopted based on the contravariant transformation of the coordinate differentials, dq^i , and the generalized velocities, \dot{q}^i .

Poisson Bracket Formulation of Hamiltonian Invariance

A transformation of the phase space variables may be expressed as a simultaneous transformation of the independent coordinates and momenta, q^i and p_i , to a new set: Q^j and P_j , having the functional form:

$$\begin{aligned} Q^j &= Q^j(q^i, p_i) \\ P_j &= P_j(q^i, p_i), \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

that is assumed to be non-singular. In the Hamiltonian formulation, we are interested in transformations preserving the canonical structure of (3.8). That is, in the new variables we must have

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}^j &= \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_j} \\ \dot{P}_j &= -\frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^j},\end{aligned}\tag{3.11}$$

where $H' = H'(Q^j, P_j)$, is a new Hamiltonian function that we will assume does not contain time as an explicit parameter. In such cases: $d_t H = \partial_t H = 0$; so the Hamiltonian function must transform as a scalar - although certainly not as a functional invariant. With this in mind we write

$$H'(Q^j, P_j) = H(q^i, p_i),\tag{3.12}$$

and note also that $H = T + V = T' + V' = H'$ is the total energy, which must be conserved for transformations between inertial frames of reference. Transformations having the functional form of (3.10), resulting in (3.11) - are defined as canonical transformations. The generating function technique (see for example Goldstein [6]) allows greater flexibility in the functional form of (3.10), but we will not discuss this method here.

Now that we have the necessary condition for a canonical transformation, we may continue by investigating the restrictions on such transformations. To begin, consider the differential of $H'(Q^j, P_j)$:

$$\begin{aligned}dH' &= \partial_{Q^k} H' dQ^k + \partial_{P_k} H' dP_k \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial q^i} \partial_{Q^k} H' + \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \partial_{P_k} H' \right) dq^i + \left(\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial p_i} \partial_{Q^k} H' + \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} \partial_{P_k} H' \right) dp_i,\end{aligned}\tag{3.13}$$

where we have substituted for the differentials dQ^k and dP_k from (3.10). Noting (3.12), and then using (3.13) we have

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{q}^i &= \partial_{p_i} H = \frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial p_i} \partial_{Q^k} H' + \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} \partial_{P_k} H' \\ \dot{p}_i &= -\partial_{q^i} H = -\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial q^i} \partial_{Q^k} H' - \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \partial_{P_k} H' .\end{aligned}\tag{3.14}$$

Considering the total time derivative of (3.10):

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}^j &= \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^i + \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} \dot{p}_i \\ \dot{P}_j &= \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial q^i} \dot{q}^i + \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial p_i} \dot{p}_i,\end{aligned}\tag{3.15}$$

and then substituting for \dot{q}^i and \dot{p}_i from (3.14) we get after cancellation:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}^j &= \left(\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} \right) \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \\ \dot{P}_j &= - \left(\frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial P_j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial Q^k}{\partial p_i} \right) \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k}.\end{aligned}\tag{3.16}$$

Comparing (3.16) with (3.11), we must have

$$\frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial p_i} - \frac{\partial P_k}{\partial q^i} \frac{\partial Q^j}{\partial p_i} \equiv [Q^j, P_k]_{PB} = \delta_k^j,\tag{3.17}$$

for the transformation to be canonical - which by definition is the Poisson bracket. Using the Poisson bracket notation, (3.16) may be expressed

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{Q}^j &= [Q^j, P_k]_{PB} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial P_k} \\ \dot{P}_j &= - [Q^k, P_j]_{PB} \frac{\partial H'}{\partial Q^k},\end{aligned}\tag{3.18}$$

demonstrating explicitly the significance of the Poisson bracket for the invariance of Hamilton's equations.

4. Tensor Forms of Hamilton's Equations

Symplectic Formulation

Consider Hamilton's equations of motion for a single degree of freedom in configuration space:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{q}^1 &= \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_1} \\ \dot{p}_1 &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial q^1},\end{aligned}\tag{4.1}$$

where the tensor index is included to mark the transformation rules of the contravariant generalized coordinate, q^1 , and the covariant conjugate momenta, p_1 . To observe the distinction between upper/lower indices, we need a metric or fundamental tensor to raise and lower indices on the conjugate variables. To construct the metric, we first make the identification:

$$(q^1, p_1) \equiv (w^1, w_1),\tag{4.2}$$

and then raise the index on the 2nd component of the tuple with our (as yet) undetermined metric a^{ij} to get

$$(w^1, w_1) \rightarrow (w^1, a^{12} w_1) = (w^1, w^2) \equiv (q^1, p^1).\tag{4.3}$$

The purpose of (4.2) is to eliminate an inconsistency that occurs when using index notation with separate kernel symbols, but there is an added feature that immediately appears: using a single kernel symbol for both coordinates and momenta requires that we distinguish the respective variables using upper and lower indices. This should not be too surprising, however, given that we have removed the labeling with different kernel symbols - but it is a very attractive feature that gives geometric interpretation to the differences between coordinates and momenta.

This distinction is especially apparent when (4.1) is expressed in terms of (4.2):

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{w}^1 &= \partial^1 H \\ \dot{w}_1 &= -\partial_1 H,\end{aligned}\tag{4.4}$$

(using $\partial^1 \equiv \frac{\partial H}{\partial w_1}$; $\partial_1 \equiv \frac{\partial H}{\partial w^1}$; etc.) giving an equation for the upper and lower case, respectively. A metric may be identified by arbitrarily requiring a contravariant transformation rule for both equations in (4.4). As already noted in the discussion of (3.12), H transforms as a scalar, i.e. $H' = H$ (but not as a functional invariant) so we have $H(q^1, p_1) = H'(w^1, w^2)$; the first equation in (4.4) becomes

$$\partial^1 H = \frac{\partial w^2}{\partial w_1} \partial_2 H = a^{12} \partial_2 H,$$

giving

$$\dot{w}^1 = a^{12} \partial_2 H.$$

For the 2nd equation first notice that $\dot{w}^2 = d(a^{12} w_1) / dt = a^{12} \dot{w}_1 + w_1 da^{12} / dt$, so

$$\dot{w}^2 = a^{12} \frac{\partial H}{\partial w^1} + w_1 \frac{da^{12}}{dt},$$

and then after combining these results we obtain the contravariant form of (4.4):

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{w}^1 &= a^{12} \frac{\partial H}{\partial w^2} \\ \dot{w}^2 &= a^{12} \frac{\partial H}{\partial w^1} + w_1 \frac{da^{12}}{dt}.\end{aligned}\tag{4.5}$$

The presence of the term, $w_1 da^{12} / dt$ is very troubling at first and spoils the canonical form of (4.4), but later we see that for canonical transformations (see (5.5)) that

$$da^{ij} / dt = 0.\tag{4.6}$$

To retain the antisymmetric structure of (4.4) we must have

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{w}^1 &= a^{12} \frac{\partial H}{\partial w^2} \\ \dot{w}^2 &= -a^{12} \frac{\partial H}{\partial w^1},\end{aligned}$$

or in matrix form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{w}^1 \\ \dot{w}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & a^{12} \\ -a^{12} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_1 H \\ \partial_2 H \end{pmatrix},$$

so that $a^{21} = -a^{12}$. Hamilton's equations imply that $a^{12} = 1$, so in index form the above may be expressed

$$\dot{w}^i = a^{ij} \partial_j H, \tag{4.7}$$

with

$$a^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{4.8}$$

The result in (4.8) is really not too surprising given the matrix form of Hamilton's equations, but the point is that (4.8) can be used to raise and lower indices to obtain the canonical form of (4.7).

To determine the general form of a^{ij} , consider the less trivial example of a 2-d configuration space. In this case, the tuple in (4.2) may be identified in 3 ways. The typical ordering of variables in the symplectic case (see for example Goldstein [6]) is given by

$$(q^1, q^2, p_1, p_2) \equiv (w^1, w^2, w_1, w_2) \Rightarrow (q^1, q^2, p^1, p^2) \equiv (w^1, w^2, w^3, w^4), \tag{4.9}$$

so when Hamilton's equations are arranged in this order, the metric must be

$$a^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{4.10}$$

For the general case of (4.9), we find that (with $I \equiv N \times N$ identity):

$$a^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & I \\ -I & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{4.11}$$

Another form of a^{ij} may be obtained from (4.9) by a simple re-arrangement:

$$(q^1, p_1, q^2, p_2) \equiv (w^1, w_1, w^2, w_2) \Rightarrow (q^1, p^1, q^2, p^2) \equiv (w^1, w^2, w^3, w^4). \tag{4.12}$$

Hamilton's equations then imply that

$$a^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.13)$$

or in general, the block diagonal form may be used

$$a^{ij} = \sum_{m=1}^N (\oplus \varepsilon^{kl})_m = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon^{kl} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon^{kl} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \varepsilon^{kl} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.14)$$

where ε^{kl} is the totally antisymmetric tensor density of weight +1. Finally we note that another form of a^{ij} follows from

$$(q^1, q^2, p_1, p_2) \equiv (w^1, w^2, w_2, w_1) \Rightarrow (q^1, q^2, p^2, p^1) \equiv (w^1, w^2, w^3, w^4), \quad (4.15)$$

giving

$$a^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.16)$$

Although (4.10), (4.13), and (4.16) are equivalent, the direct sum construction of (4.14) \Rightarrow (4.13) is preferable for aesthetic reasons (see the discussion below (4.30) and in addition, the comments by Hammermesh [21] - p. 405).

Unitary Formulation

Consider Hamilton's equations for the case of a 2-d phase space:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{q}^1 \\ \dot{p}_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_{p_1} H \\ \partial_{q^1} H \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.17)$$

It is possible to complexify Hamilton's equations (see the discussion in the Introduction) by simply combining q and p as

$$z = q^1 + i p_1. \quad (4.18)$$

The complex form of (4.17) may be obtained by multiplying the second equation by i , and then adding the equations together to get

$$\dot{z} = -2i \partial_{\bar{z}} H, \quad (4.19)$$

where \bar{z} is complex conjugate to z . But as discussed in the Introduction, the definition in (4.18) is less than satisfactory for several reasons. These difficulties are naturally resolved by choosing a basis in which the metric in (4.17) is diagonal. To find such a basis we seek linear combinations of q^1 and p_1 that remain invariant under the action of a^{ij} (except possibly for a scale factor λ), i.e. we allow a^{ij} to produce vectors that are parallel to the original vector - resulting in the classic eigenvalue-eigenvector problem. Specifically, we solve

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{i1} \\ c_{i2} \end{pmatrix} = \lambda_i \begin{pmatrix} c_{i1} \\ c_{i2} \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} - \lambda_i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\} \begin{pmatrix} c_{i1} \\ c_{i2} \end{pmatrix} = 0, \quad (4.20)$$

so we must have, $\det(a^{ij} - \lambda \delta^{ij}) = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda = \pm i$. The eigenvectors have the general form:

$$\psi_i = c_{i1} q + c_{i2} p,$$

so c_{i1} and c_{i2} must satisfy:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1; \begin{pmatrix} i & 1 \\ -1 & i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} \\ c_{12} \end{pmatrix} = 0 &\Rightarrow c_{11} = 1, c_{12} = -i \\ \lambda_2; \begin{pmatrix} -i & 1 \\ -1 & -i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{21} \\ c_{22} \end{pmatrix} = 0 &\Rightarrow c_{11} = 1, c_{12} = i, \end{aligned}$$

giving

$$\{q^1 + i p_1, q^1 - i p_1\} = \{z, \bar{z}\} \in \mathbb{C}^2, \quad (4.21)$$

with eigenbasis $(1, i), (1, -i)$. These eigenvectors are the new dynamical variables - elements of a linear vector space in which a^{ij} is diagonal. Using (3.18), the Hamiltonian structure may be quickly examined in the new basis by calculating the Poisson bracket of:

$$Q \equiv z, P \equiv \bar{z}, \tag{4.22}$$

giving immediately the diagonal form of (4.17):

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{z} \\ \dot{\bar{z}} \end{pmatrix} = 2 \begin{pmatrix} -i & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_{\bar{z}} H \\ \partial_z H \end{pmatrix} = 2 \overline{\begin{pmatrix} +i & 0 \\ 0 & -i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_z H \\ \partial_{\bar{z}} H \end{pmatrix}}, \tag{4.23}$$

expressed on the RHS using complex conjugation. But upon comparison with (3.17), we see immediately that the transformation (4.22) is not canonical because of the factor i appearing in (4.23). However, the transformation could be made canonical by including a factor: $(i)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ in (4.22), or by letting $P \equiv \bar{z}/i$, or also by absorbing i into the Hamiltonian function: $\tilde{H} = iH$. Note also that the factor of 2 may be eliminated by choosing:

$$z = \frac{q^1 + i p_1}{\sqrt{2}}; \bar{z} = \frac{q^1 - i p_1}{\sqrt{2}}. \tag{4.24}$$

Schouten's Hybrid-Index Method

Tensor indices may be added by utilizing the 'hybrid quantities' introduced by Schouten (see [2,10] pp. 51 and 240, respectively). Using this approach, general tensor quantities having both real and imaginary components may be incorporated into transformation theory. Complex conjugation is symbolized using bars over indices, e.g. $\overline{A^k} \equiv A^{\bar{k}}$, and the geometric distinction of co and contravariant indices may be expressed indirectly by the complex conjugation of indices. The raising and lowering of indices may be performed as usual with a metric

$$a_{k\bar{j}} z^{\bar{j}} = z_k; a^{i\bar{i}} z_{\bar{i}} = z^i, \text{ etc.},$$

but now the metric, $a_{k\bar{j}}$, is a mixed 2nd rank hybrid quantity. If $a_{k\bar{j}}$ satisfies

$$a_{k\bar{j}} = (a_{k\bar{j}})^\dagger = a_{j\bar{k}},$$

then $a_{k\bar{j}}$ is hermitian by definition (where \dagger signifies the complex conjugate transpose \equiv adjoint) and a space equipped with such a metric is defined as a hermitian manifold designated as a U_n (see [10] - p. 242). Another case to consider is the anti-hermitian case, that is:

$$a_{k\bar{j}} = -a_{j\bar{k}},$$

which may be obtained from the hermitian form by multiplication by i - although we will not consider this here. We see immediately that if the inner product of two complex vectors:

$$\langle A, B \rangle \equiv a_{j\bar{k}} A^j B^{\bar{k}} \equiv A^j B_j \equiv A_{\bar{k}} B^{\bar{k}},$$

is required to be real, then $a_{k\bar{j}}$ must be hermitian.

Interestingly, the hybrid notation of Schouten is fully equivalent to the *bra-ket* notation invented for the purposes of quantum theory by Dirac [11]. The inner product given above may be expressed in Dirac's matrix notation by $\langle A|B \rangle$, so the correspondence between the two notations is

$$bra \equiv \langle B| \Rightarrow B^{\bar{k}} \text{ or } B_k ; ket \equiv |A \rangle \Rightarrow A^k \text{ or } A_{\bar{k}},$$

and indeed, calculations in quantum mechanics may be carried out using the hybrid index method. A further discussion of this correspondence can be found in Schouten [10] - p. 250. Another similarity with the quantum formalism should be mentioned; namely, that the eigenvectors given in (4.24) are formally identical to the raising and lowering operators of quantum mechanics, but with an important distinction: in quantum theory q and p are operators. Also, the time evolution of a system is not represented by points in phase space, but rather by states in Hilbert space.

Using the hybrid-index notation the complex eigenvectors (4.24), may now be assigned indices which may be raised or lowered with a metric:

$$z^1 \equiv z_{\bar{1}} = \frac{q^1 + ip_1}{\sqrt{2}} ; z^{\bar{1}} \equiv z_1 = \frac{q^1 - ip_1}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (4.25)$$

and the dynamical equations are thus

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{z}^1 \\ \dot{z}_1 \end{pmatrix} = -i \begin{pmatrix} \partial_{z_1} H \\ \partial_{z^1} H \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \dot{z}^1 \\ \dot{z}^{\bar{1}} \end{pmatrix} = i \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_{\bar{1}} H \\ \partial_1 H \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.26)$$

Note that in this version of Hamiltonian mechanics the dynamical variables are literally “conjugate” to one another. Equation (4.26) should be compared with (4.4) - where it is brought out that the coordinates and momenta are given geometric distinction as contravariant/covariant quantities, respectively. Not surprisingly, this distinction is carried over to the complex formalism as shown in (4.26), but now with the new index operation of complex conjugation. In index form, (4.26) may be expressed

$$\dot{z}^k = -i a^{k\bar{k}} \partial_{\bar{k}} H \equiv \left[i a^{\bar{k}k} \partial_k H \right]^\dagger, \quad (4.27)$$

with $a^{\bar{k}k}$ given by

$$a^{\bar{k}k} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \equiv \varepsilon^{\bar{k}k}, \quad (4.28)$$

which we will denote as the unitary or diagonal form of ε^{kl} - with a complex over-bar as indicated above.

Equation (4.27) has been defined with a hermitian metric (4.28), but may also be expressed in anti-hermitian form:

$$\dot{z}^k = a^{k\bar{k}} \partial_{\bar{k}} H \equiv \left[a^{\bar{k}k} \partial_k H \right]^\dagger, \quad (4.29)$$

in which case

$$a^{\bar{k}k} = \begin{pmatrix} +i & 0 \\ 0 & -i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.30)$$

although as we have noted previously, we will not consider the case of (4.30).

As mentioned earlier, the direct sum construction given by (4.14) is preferable for aesthetic reasons that should be apparent given the ordering chosen in (4.12). If a given configuration space has dimension N , then (4.26) may be generalized to \mathbb{C}^{2N} by individually diagonalizing the block sub-matrices of (4.14). Since the $2N$ eigenvectors of this procedure are linearly independent, the resulting eigenspace, \mathbb{C}^{2N} , may be constructed from the direct sum of the individual invariant eigenspaces. To clarify, consider the definition of an invariant subspace (see Hoffman [22], p.199):

Definition: If V is a linear vector space and T is a linear transformation on V , then if K is a subspace of V we say that K is invariant if for every $\alpha \in K$, the vector $T\alpha$ is in K , i.e. $T(K)$ is contained in K .

The definition may be verified almost trivially for the case considered here. Interestingly, if we regard a^{ij} as a raising/lowering operator, the invariant vectors of a^{ij} are given by (4.20). Each subspace formed in this fashion is then invariant under the action of the constituent, ε^{kl} , from which a^{ij} is constructed. To summarize, the ε^{kl} are regarded independent in the sense that individual variables are independent. For low dimensional cases (i.e. 1-d configuration space) we will use the notation

$$a^{kl} \equiv \varepsilon^{kl},$$

or in the 2×2 unitary case:

$$a^{\bar{k}l} \equiv \varepsilon^{\bar{k}l},$$

so that the meaning is clear regarding the dimension of phase space. We will denote the metric by a^{kl} when referring to higher dimensional cases.

5. Canonical Transformation Theory

Given the formalism developed in the preceding sections, a study of Hamiltonian invariance follows using tensor transformation theory. As pointed out in Section 3, an important aspect of the Hamiltonian formulation is the study of transformations preserving the Hamiltonian structure, i.e. transformations preserving the form of (3.8). In fact, we have already obtained the condition for canonical invariance in (3.17), but in this section we wish to bring out other features by studying the invariance of (4.8) and (4.27) or equivalently (4.28) - but in particular we are interested in transformations of (4.28) induced by the canonical invariance of (4.8).

Symplectic

The invariance of (4.8) is most easily studied by considering a transformation of (4.7) using the contravariant transformation rules of the \dot{w}^i . Given a nonsingular transformation of coordinates

$$w^i \rightarrow w'^k = w'^k(w^i), \quad (5.1)$$

the new components may be expressed in terms of the old by

$$\dot{w}'^k = (\partial_i w'^k) \dot{w}^i = \partial_i w'^k a^{ij} \partial_j H,$$

where (4.7) has been used to obtain the RHS. Again, as it has already been noted in the discussion of (3.12), H transforms as a scalar, i.e. $H' = H$ (but not a functional invariant) so we have

$$\partial_j H' = \partial_j w'^l \partial_l H,$$

giving the transformation of (4.7):

$$\dot{w}'^k = \partial_i w'^k \partial_j w'^l a^{ij} \partial_l H'. \quad (5.2)$$

From (5.2) it is apparent that the new metric is

$$a'^{kl} = \partial_i w'^k \partial_j w'^l a^{ij}, \quad (5.3)$$

so in the case of 2-dimensional phase space we write

$$\varepsilon'^{kl} = \partial_i w'^k \partial_j w'^l \varepsilon^{ij} = \det(A) \varepsilon^{kl}, \quad (5.4)$$

using the transformation properties of ε'^{kl} and with $A \equiv A_j^i$; denoting the Jacobian matrix of the transformation. From (5.4) we see that

$$\det(A) = 1 \neq \det(A)(w), \quad (5.5)$$

if the transformation is canonical, given that for canonical invariance: $\varepsilon'^{kl} = \varepsilon^{kl}$ - which justifies the assumption in (4.6) that $da^{ij}/dt = 0$, i.e. there is no coordinate dependence as in the Riemannian case discussed in [1]. Using the Poisson bracket notation we notice that the components of ε'^{kl} may be defined with the free-indices (and antisymmetry) of the bracket:

$$\varepsilon'^{kl} = [w'^k, w'^l]_{PB} = \partial_i w'^k \partial_j w'^l \varepsilon^{ij}, \quad (5.6)$$

so for canonical invariance the Poisson bracket condition may be defined by

$$[w'^k, w'^l]_{PB} = \det(A) \varepsilon^{kl}. \quad (5.7)$$

Comparing (5.7) with (3.17), we see that a difference arises between the Poisson bracket conditions in ordinary canonical form, and those obtained from a tensor formulation of Hamilton's equations. For higher dimensional cases, the condition for canonical invariance is:

$$[w'^k, w'^l]_{PB} = \partial_i w'^k \partial_j w'^l a^{ij} = \det(A) a^{kl}, \quad (5.8)$$

where a^{kl} is constructed from (4.14). Substituting (5.8) into (4.7) we get finally

$$\dot{w}'^k = [w'^k, w'^l]_{PB} \partial_l H', \quad (5.9)$$

which should be compared with (3.18).

The contravariant form of Hamilton's equations in (4.7) is completely arbitrary, i.e. we could have expressed the equations in terms of the covariant variables w_i :

$$\dot{w}_i = a_{ij} \partial^j H, \quad (5.10)$$

but now we see an interestingly distinction between the two forms: the invariance of (5.10) leads immediately to the definition of the Lagrange bracket given by

$$\left[w'_k, w'_l \right]_{LB} = \partial_{k'} w^i \partial_{l'} w_i - \partial_{k'} w_i \partial_{l'} w^i, \quad (5.11)$$

as opposed to the Poisson bracket result for the invariance of (4.7). The result is obtained by transforming (5.10) to get

$$\dot{w}'_k = \partial_{k'} w^i \partial_{l'} w^j a_{ij} \partial^{l'} H',$$

giving

$$a'_{kl} = \partial_{k'} w^i \partial_{l'} w^j a_{ij},$$

and leads to the analogous result of (5.8):

$$a_{kl} = \left[w'_k, w'_l \right]_{LB},$$

using the definition in (5.11).

Unitary

Now consider the invariance of (4.27):

$$\dot{z}^i = -i a^{ij} \partial_j H,$$

given a non-singular transformation of coordinates

$$z^i \rightarrow z'^k = z'^k(z^i, z^{\bar{i}}), \quad (5.12)$$

$$H \rightarrow H' = H'(z'^l, z'^{\bar{l}}). \quad (5.13)$$

The total time derivative of (5.12) is

$$\dot{z}'^k = \partial_i z'^k \dot{z}^i + \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k \dot{z}^{\bar{i}},$$

and then after substituting for z^i and $z^{\bar{i}}$ from above we get

$$\dot{z}'^k = \partial_i z'^k (-i a^{i\bar{j}} \partial_j H) + \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k (i a^{\bar{i}j} \partial_j H), \quad (5.14)$$

but since

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_j H &= \partial_j H' = \partial_i H' \partial_j z'^i + \partial_{\bar{i}} H' \partial_j z'^{\bar{i}} \\ \partial_{\bar{j}} H &= \partial_{\bar{j}} H' = \partial_i H' \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^i + \partial_{\bar{i}} H' \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}}, \end{aligned}$$

(5.14) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}'^k &= -i a^{i\bar{j}} \left[\partial_i H' \partial_i z'^k \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}} + \partial_{\bar{i}} H' \partial_i z'^k \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}} \right] \\ &\quad + i a^{\bar{i}j} \left[\partial_i H' \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k \partial_j z'^i + \partial_{\bar{i}} H' \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k \partial_j z'^i \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Collecting factors of the Hamiltonian derivative, the above may be rewritten

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{z}'^k &= i \left[a^{\bar{i}j} \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k \partial_j z'^i - a^{i\bar{j}} \partial_i z'^k \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}} \right] \partial_i H' \\ &\quad - i \left[a^{i\bar{j}} \partial_i z'^k \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}} - a^{\bar{i}j} \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k \partial_j z'^i \right] \partial_{\bar{i}} H', \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

but given the hermitian properties of $a^{i\bar{j}} = a^{j\bar{i}} = a^{\bar{i}j}$, the first term in (5.15) cancels and we are left with

$$\dot{z}'^k = -i a^{i\bar{j}} \left[\partial_i z'^k \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}} - \partial_{\bar{i}} z'^k \partial_j z'^i \right] \partial_{\bar{i}} H'. \quad (5.16)$$

or

$$\dot{z}'^k = -i \left[z'^k, z'^{\bar{i}} \right]_{PB} \partial_{\bar{i}} H', \quad (5.17)$$

which should be compared with (3.18) and (5.9). As in the symplectic case, the condition for canonical invariance is $a'^{k\bar{i}} = a^{k\bar{i}}$, denoting $\partial_i z'^k$ by $U_{,i}^k \equiv U$:

$$a'^{k\bar{i}} = \left[z'^k, z'^{\bar{i}} \right]_{PB} = \det(U) a^{k\bar{i}}. \quad (5.18)$$

Referring to the transformation in (5.12), we note the functional dependence on both $(z^i, z^{\bar{i}})$.

As we will later show in Section 6, transformations having this functional form are non-analytic in the sense that the Cauchy-Riemann conditions are not satisfied. Assuming for the moment that (5.12) is analytic, we have (noting that the functional form of (5.19) is not a sufficient condition for analyticity):

$$z^i \rightarrow z'^k = z'^k(z^i), \quad (5.19)$$

and then (5.16) may be expressed

$$\dot{z}'^k = -i \partial_i z'^k \partial_{\bar{j}} z'^{\bar{i}} a^{i\bar{j}} \partial_{\bar{i}} H'.$$

Again using $\partial_i z'^k \equiv U_{.i}^k$, we may write the metric transformation as (compare with Schouten [2] - p.

55)

$$a'^{k\bar{i}} = U_{.i}^k U_{.j}^{\bar{i}} a^{i\bar{j}}, \quad (5.20)$$

implying that

$$a'^{k\bar{i}} = U^{k\bar{j}} U_{.j}^{\bar{i}}.$$

Multiplying both sides by $a_{\bar{i}i}$ we get

$$\delta_i^k = U^{k\bar{j}} U_{i\bar{j}}, \quad (5.21)$$

but for proper matrix multiplication we see that the 2nd term is actually the adjoint: $(U_{j\bar{i}})^\dagger = U_{i\bar{j}}$, so we may express (5.21) alternatively in matrix notation:

$$U^\dagger U = I,$$

where I is the $2N \times 2N$ identity. Transformations satisfying (5.21) are defined as unitary transformations; so by considering the analytic form of (5.12), we bring out the classification we have been seeking: namely, that canonical invariance of (4.7) (or equivalently (3.18)) is equivalent to the unitary invariance of (4.28). Note that we might have deduced this already from (4.28), given the hermitian character of $a^{k\bar{i}}$, but by considering the special case of a non-analytic transformation, we make contact with the usual definition in (5.21) - while emphasizing that the Poisson bracket condition gives an alternative expression of unitary invariance for the non-analytic case - although we are not claiming here that non-analytic transformations can be unitary. The sub-Section entitled "Unitary Formulation" of Section 4 derives its name from the invariance of (4.28) - although we have had to wait some time to see it.

Rotation of the Phase Plane

For the next 2 sub-Sections we give some examples involving rotations and harmonic oscillators. The purpose is not so much to give applications or show new advantages obtained from the previous results, but rather to illustrate the notation by considering a few simple cases.

Probably the simplest example to consider is a rotation of the phase plane for the case of 2-d phase space. A clockwise rotation of the vector (w^1, w^2) may be expressed

$$\begin{pmatrix} w'^1 \\ w'^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos\theta & -\sin\theta \\ \sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} w^1 \\ w^2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.22)$$

and the Poisson bracket given by (5.6) has the components

$$\varepsilon'^{kl} = \begin{pmatrix} [w'^1, w'^1]_{PB} & [w'^1, w'^2]_{PB} \\ [w'^2, w'^1]_{PB} & [w'^2, w'^2]_{PB} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \cos^2\theta + \sin^2\theta \\ -\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

demonstrating as expected, the canonical invariance of (4.7). Given the transformation (5.22), we find the corresponding transformation for $(z^1, z^{\bar{1}})$ by writing

$$\begin{aligned} z'^1 &= w'^1 + i w'^2 = w^1 \cos\theta - w^2 \sin\theta + i(w^1 \sin\theta + w^2 \cos\theta) \\ &= \cos\theta (w^1 + i w^2) + i \sin\theta (w^1 + i w^2) \\ z'^1 &= e^{i\theta} z^1, \end{aligned} \quad (5.23)$$

but given the functional dependence, $z' = z'(z)$, (as in (5.19)) we have immediately that $z'^{\bar{1}} = e^{-i\theta} z^{\bar{1}}$, showing that (5.22) has the unitary counterpart:

$$\begin{pmatrix} z'^1 \\ z'^{\bar{1}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\theta} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-i\theta} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} z^1 \\ z^{\bar{1}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5.24)$$

but noting that (5.23) contains the essential result. The invariance of (4.27) follows easily from (5.17) and we have

$$\dot{z}^1 = -i \left[e^{i\theta} e^{-i\theta} - 0 \right]_{PB} \partial_{z^1} H' = -i \partial_{z^1} H'.$$

The Harmonic Oscillator

The Hamiltonian for a 1-d harmonic oscillator may be expressed

$$H = \frac{p_1^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2} m \omega^2 x^1,$$

where $\omega = \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}}$ is the frequency of oscillation. Choosing

$$z^1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} (m\omega q^1 + i p_1),$$

we see that H may be expressed rather simply as $H = z^1 z^{\bar{1}}$. Calculating the Poisson bracket of $Q = z^1$

and $P = z^{\bar{1}}$ we get

$$\left[z^1, z^{\bar{1}} \right]_{PB} = -i\omega,$$

so Hamilton's equations may be expressed by the single equation (the 2nd equation is redundant):

$$\dot{z}^1 = -i\omega \partial_{z^{\bar{1}}} H = -i\omega z^1. \quad (5.25)$$

Equation (5.25) is integrated immediately to give a solution generated by a unitary transformation of the initial state:

$$z^1(t) = z^1(0) e^{-i\omega t},$$

which may be separated into real and imaginary parts:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \operatorname{Re} z^1(t) \\ \operatorname{Im} z^1(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} q^1 \\ p_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m\omega \cos \omega t & -\sin \omega t \\ \sin \omega t & m\omega \cos \omega t \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} q^1(0) \\ p_1(0) \end{pmatrix}$$

expressed as a counter-clockwise rotation in state space.

Consider the case of 2-coupled harmonic oscillators of equal mass and spring constant, k . The Lagrangian is given by

$$L = T - V = \frac{1}{2}m(\dot{q}^1)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m(\dot{q}^2)^2 - \frac{1}{2}k(q^1)^2 - \frac{1}{2}k(q^2)^2 - \frac{1}{2}k(q^1 - q^2)^2,$$

which we may rewrite as

$$L = \frac{1}{2}T_{ij}\dot{q}^i\dot{q}^j - \frac{1}{2}V_{ij}q^i q^j,$$

using

$$T_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} m & 0 \\ 0 & m \end{pmatrix}; V_{ij} = k \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.26)$$

The conjugate momenta are calculated: $p_i = \partial_{\dot{q}^i} L = T_{ij}\dot{q}^j$, so the Hamiltonian in this case is

$$H = p_i\dot{q}^i - L = \frac{1}{2}T_{ij}\dot{q}^i\dot{q}^j + \frac{1}{2}V_{ij}q^i q^j,$$

but in terms of the conjugate momenta we have

$$H = \frac{1}{2}T^{ij} p_i p_j + \frac{1}{2}V_{ij}q^i q^j, \quad (5.27)$$

with

$$T^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 1/m & 0 \\ 0 & 1/m \end{pmatrix}.$$

The off diagonal elements of V_{ij} in (5.26) gives the coupling between the oscillators, but we may decouple the system by introducing a basis in which V_{ij} is diagonal. The invariant vectors in this representation (eigenvectors) may be expressed as a linear combination of q^1 and q^2 :

$Q^i = c_1^i q^1 + c_2^i q^2$, and are found by solving:

$$\left\{ k \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & 1 \end{pmatrix} - \lambda_i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^i \\ c_2^i \end{pmatrix} = 0.$$

The eigenvalues are given by $\det(V_{ij} - \lambda_i \delta_{ij}) = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda = 1 \pm \frac{1}{2}$. The eigenvectors, Q^1 and Q^2 are then

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{3}{2}; \quad k \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^1 \\ c_2^1 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \Rightarrow Q^1 = q^1 - q^2$$

$$\lambda_2 = \frac{1}{2}; \quad k \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 \\ c_2^2 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \Rightarrow Q^2 = q^1 + q^2,$$

and for the corresponding momenta:

$$P_1 = p_1 - p_2$$

$$P_2 = p_1 + p_2.$$

In the normal modes basis, (5.27) may be expressed

$$H = \frac{P_1^2}{2m} + \frac{P_2^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2} m \omega_1^2 (Q^1)^2 + \frac{1}{2} m \omega_2^2 (Q^2)^2, \quad (5.28)$$

with $\omega_1 = \sqrt{\frac{k_1}{m}}$, $\omega_2 = \sqrt{\frac{k_2}{m}}$ and $k_1 = \frac{3}{2}k$, $k_2 = \frac{1}{2}k$, for the antisymmetric and symmetric modes,

respectively.

Given the form of (5.28) we may express H as

$$H = z^1 z_1 + z^2 z_2, \quad (5.29)$$

using

$$z^1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} (m\omega_1 Q^1 + iP_1); \quad z^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2m}} (m\omega_2 Q^2 + iP_2).$$

Hamilton's equations are nearly identical to the 1-d case and we get the de-coupled system

$$\dot{z}^1 = -i\omega_1 \partial_{z^1} H = -i\omega_1 z^1$$

$$\dot{z}^2 = -i\omega_2 \partial_{z^2} H = -i\omega_2 z^2, \quad (5.30)$$

with solutions given by

$$z^1(t) = z^1(0) e^{-i\omega_1 t}$$

$$z^2(t) = z^2(0) e^{-i\omega_2 t}.$$

6. Analytic Structure in Hamiltonian Mechanics

Analytic Functions

A central theme in the study of complex function theory is the existence of the derivative, and its consequences for the structural and analytic properties of complex functions. By definition (see Ahlfors [23]), an analytic function must possess a derivative everywhere the function is defined. If a function, $z'(z)$ is analytic at a point z_0 , then

$$\frac{d}{dz} z'(z_0) \equiv d_z z'(z_0),$$

must not only exist at z_0 , but at every point in a neighborhood of z_0 , i.e. $d_z z'(z_0)$ is defined for:

$$\forall z \in \left\{ |z - z_0| < r ; (r \neq 0) \in \mathbb{R} \right\}.$$

The conditions that must be satisfied for analyticity are the so-called Cauchy-Riemann equations (that will be derived below) for complex functions of a single complex variable: $z'(z) : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, with

$$z' = x' + i y', \tag{6.1}$$

and

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} x \rightarrow x'(x, y) \\ y \rightarrow y'(x, y) \end{array} \right\} z \rightarrow z'(z).$$

The existence of $d_z z'(z_0)$ is implied by the uniqueness of the derivative at a single point in the complex plane - otherwise we are led to a contradiction. First consider the coordinate differential of $z'(z)$:

$$dz' = (\partial_x x' + i \partial_x y') dx + (\partial_y x' + i \partial_y y') dy,$$

so the derivative of $z'(z)$ may be expressed

$$d_z z'(z) = \frac{(\partial_x x' + i \partial_x y') dx + (\partial_y x' + i \partial_y y') dy}{dx + i dy}. \quad (6.2)$$

Now, evaluating the derivative at z_0 and approaching along a path: $dy = 0$, (6.2) becomes

$$d_z z'(z) \Big|_{z \rightarrow z_0}^1 = (\partial_x x' + i \partial_x y') \Big|_{z \rightarrow z_0}^1 = \partial_x z'. \quad (6.3)$$

Along the path: $dx = 0$, we get

$$d_z z'(z) \Big|_{z \rightarrow z_0}^2 = (\partial_y y' - i \partial_y x') \Big|_{z \rightarrow z_0}^2 = -i \partial_y z'. \quad (6.4)$$

But since we must have

$$d_z z'(z_0) \Big|_1^1 = d_z z'(z_0) \Big|_2^2 \quad (\text{or equivalently } \partial_x z' = -i \partial_y z'), \quad (6.5)$$

the existence of the derivative is implied by the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_x x' &= \partial_y y' \\ \partial_y x' &= -\partial_x y', \end{aligned} \quad (6.6)$$

which are the Cauchy-Riemann conditions for an analytic function.

As an alternative expression of analyticity (but still deriving from (6.5)) we consider a complex function of 2 real variables, $z' = z'(x, y)$. But since $z = x + iy$ and $\bar{z} = x - iy$ we have

$$x = \frac{1}{2}(z + \bar{z}) ; \quad y = \frac{1}{2i}(z - \bar{z}), \quad (6.7)$$

and so we may express z' as a function: $z'(z, \bar{z})$, regarding z and \bar{z} as linearly independent variables

(see NOTE below (6.10)). Considering the coordinate differential of z' we have

$$dz' = \partial_x z' dx + \partial_y z' dy, \quad (6.8)$$

but then after substituting for dx and dy from (6.7) and collecting terms, (6.8) becomes

$$dz' = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_x z' - i \partial_y z') dz + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_x z' + i \partial_y z') d\bar{z},$$

giving

$$d_z z' = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_x z' - i \partial_y z') ; \quad d_{\bar{z}} z' = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_x z' + i \partial_y z'). \quad (6.9)$$

From (6.5) we see that for an analytic function:

$$d_{\bar{z}} z' = 0, \quad (6.10)$$

as discussed previously in relation to the functional form of (5.12). If analyticity may be characterized by (6.10), then we see immediately from (5.13) that in the unitary formulation of mechanics the Hamiltonian function is not an analytic function. This is an interesting result given that H is the total energy; a further discussion will be taken up in a later study.

NOTE: The linear independence of z and \bar{z} may be proven by solving

$$\alpha z + \beta \bar{z} = 0, \quad (6.11)$$

for $(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathbb{R}$. Taking the complex conjugate of the above we have the system:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ \beta & \alpha \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} z \\ \bar{z} \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

so we must have

$$|\alpha|^2 - |\beta|^2 = 0.$$

The equation has the 2 solutions: $\alpha = \beta$ or just $\alpha = \beta = 0$. Substituting the $\alpha = \beta$ case into (6.11) we must have $z = 0$, which is trivial. The only solution is then $\alpha = \beta = 0$; so by the definition of linear independence (6.11) is satisfied.

Conformal Invariance

Given the definition of analyticity above, we may classify and give geometric significance to transformations satisfying (6.6). Consider a curve γ in the complex plane parametrized by a scalar t , i.e. $z = z(t)$. A mapping $z'(t)$ produces a new curve γ' in the z' plane. Assuming that $z'(z(t))$ is analytic we have

$$\dot{z}'(t) = d_z z'(z) \dot{z}(t). \quad (6.12)$$

Now consider (6.12) evaluated at a point $z_0 = z(t_0)$ with $\dot{z}_0 \neq 0$ and $d_z z'(z) \neq 0$. With this assumption we immediately conclude that $\dot{z}'(z_0) \neq 0 \Rightarrow \gamma'$ has a tangent at $t = t_0$. Since every complex number has a polar representation, i.e. $z = |z| e^{i\theta}$ with $\arg z \equiv \theta$, the direction of the tangent at $t = t_0$ will be given by θ . The direction of the tangent at $t = t_0$ on γ' is found from (6.12):

$$\arg \dot{z}'(t) = \arg d_z z'(z) + \arg \dot{z}(t),$$

so the angle between the tangents to γ at z_0 and to γ' at z'_0 is then

$$\arg \dot{z}'(t_0) - \arg \dot{z}(t_0) = \arg d_z z'(z_0),$$

showing that the angle is independent of the curve γ . Therefore, mappings of intersecting curves at a given point and angle preserve the angle of intersection between the curves - given that the derivative exists.

Another property of the transformations may be brought out by considering the transformation of an infinitesimal element of length along γ which is given by

$$ds^2 = |dz|^2 = dz d\bar{z},$$

corresponding to the element on γ' :

$$ds'^2 = dz' d\bar{z}' = |d_z z'(z)|^2 dz d\bar{z} = |d_z z'(z)|^2 ds^2,$$

so in general we see that lengths will not be preserved. Substituting for $|d_z z'(z)|^2$ using say (6.3), the transformation may be expressed

$$ds'^2 = [(\partial_x x')^2 + (\partial_x y')^2] ds^2,$$

but after substituting (6.6) we get finally

$$ds'^2 = (\partial_x x' \partial_y y' - \partial_y x' \partial_x y') ds^2, \quad (6.13)$$

which is $\neq 0$ unless $z' = \text{const.}$. Transformations preserving angles but not necessarily scale are defined as conformal transformations, and we see from the definition that these properties follow directly from the existence of the derivative.

Canonical \subseteq Conformal Invariance

Now that we have given some definitions and discussion of complex analytic structure, it is interesting to consider a relation between canonical invariance and analytic transformations - given the complexification in (4.18). The correspondence follows by considering the preservation of distance in the (Q^1, P_1) plane (or indeed the (w'^1, w'^2) plane). To this end, consider a 1-d configuration space and the transformation given by (3.10):

$$\begin{aligned} Q^1 &= Q^1(q^1, p_1) \\ P_1 &= P_1(q^1, p_1). \end{aligned} \tag{6.14}$$

The transformation (6.14) may be identified with the complex mapping:

$$z^1 = q^1 + i p_1 \rightarrow z'^1 = Q^1 + i P_1.$$

To preserve distance, we see from the discussion in the preceding section that

$$ds'^2 = |d_z z'(z)|^2 ds^2 \Rightarrow (dQ^1)^2 + (dP_1)^2 = |d_z z'(z)|^2 [(dq^1)^2 + (dp_1)^2], \tag{6.15}$$

so we must have

$$|d_z z'(z)|^2 = 1.$$

But if the transformation $z \rightarrow z'(z)$ is analytic, we see from (6.13) that this is equivalent to

$$\partial_{q^1} Q^1 \partial_{p_1} P_1 - \partial_{p_1} Q^1 \partial_{q^1} P_1 = 1,$$

which is just the Poisson bracket condition for canonical invariance, i.e. $[Q^1, P_1]_{PB} = 1$. Therefore, when considering dynamics in the complex plane, the Cauchy-Riemann conditions for analyticity imply the canonical invariance of Hamilton's equations. If the Poisson bracket relation is generalized to an arbitrary scale factor, i.e. $[Q^1, P_1]_{PB} = \lambda$, $\lambda \equiv \text{const.}$, then we see that the antisymmetric structure of Hamilton's equations is preserved to within an arbitrary (but constant) factor λ . Taking this as a more general definition of canonical invariance, Hamilton's equations are then conformally invariant - from which canonical invariance derives as a special case: $\lambda = 1$. It should be pointed out, however, that

Hamilton's equations are not invariant under all conformal transformations, for in general, conformal invariance includes locally varying scale factors, i.e. $\lambda = \lambda(z)$. If this were the case we would have

$$a'^{kl} = \lambda(w) a^{kl},$$

from (5.4) but then, $da'^{kl}/dt \neq 0$, and the canonical structure of the equations is destroyed as discussed in [1] and below (4.5). But we still find it desirable to identify Hamiltonian invariance with conformal invariance, given the relation to analytic transformations as discussed above - but only in this restricted sense.

Given these results, another interpretation may be given to the relation between Q^1 and P_1 of (6.14). Referring to (6.6), if we differentiate the 1st equation with respect to x , and the 2nd with respect to y , and then add we get

$$\partial_x^2 x' + \partial_y^2 x' = 0, \quad (6.16)$$

or likewise

$$\partial_x^2 y' + \partial_y^2 y' = 0, \quad (6.17)$$

which in either case gives Laplace's equation. If a complex function, (6.1), is constructed from x' and y' satisfying both (6.16) and (6.17), then x' and y' are defined as *harmonic conjugates*. To identify with Hamiltonian systems: $x' \equiv Q^1$ and $y' \equiv P_1$, so in the case that (6.14) is canonical, Q^1 and P_1 are harmonic conjugates. Therefore, given one half of (6.14) satisfying (6.16) (or (6.17)) it will be possible in principle to construct a canonical transformation using the standard technique in complex variable theory of finding the harmonic conjugate of a harmonic function. At first glance, the idea looks promising from the viewpoint of using generating functions to construct canonical transformations - but we will leave this topic to a later investigation.

7. Discussion

In this paper we have presented 2 consistent tensor-index formulations of Hamilton's equations. By postulating a fundamental tensor for the raising/lowering of tensor indices, we have first considered the usual symplectic approach for unifying the conjugate variables into a single vector quantity. The metric is deduced from the canonical structure of the equations and defines the Poisson bracket condition for invariance. The second formulation is obtained from the first by introducing a basis for which the antisymmetric metric of the symplectic formulation is diagonal. The eigenvectors in this representation are the complex dynamical variables, z^k and $z^{\bar{k}}$, and the corresponding tensor form of the equations is given by utilizing the hybrid-index notation due to Schouten.

The motivation for investigating these formulations has been to provide a framework for a tensor transformation theory of canonical invariance - and to setup a study of the differential geometry of phase space. Although we have not attempted to address every topic that arises in the study of Hamiltonian invariance (e.g. generating functions, Hamilton Jacobi theory, etc.); we have shown that the tensor notation can be very useful, and offers additional insight into the structural properties of the equations. One of the most interesting results is that canonical invariance of the symplectic form implies the unitary invariance of the complex form. This relationship has also been noted by other authors [24, 25], but from the context of symplectic invariance in group theory where it is usually expressed:

$$Sp(N) = Sp(N, \mathbb{C}) \cap U(2N),$$

where $Sp(N)$ is the set of all $2N \times 2N$ matrices preserving (4.11).

Another interesting relation is the correspondence between analytic structure and the Poisson bracket condition for canonical invariance for the case of a single complex dynamical variable. The goal in this approach has been to encode as much of the dynamics as possible into complex analytic form - and then investigate the solutions and invariance of the equations using techniques from complex variable

theory. Although we have not gone very far with this program, we have at least set the stage for it by demonstrating the relationship between analyticity and *canonical* \subseteq *conformal* invariance.

Of possible extensions, one of the most interesting possibilities for further study involves the connection and curvature quantities defined by (2.16) and (2.18), respectively. The corresponding definitions for the Hamiltonian phase space (for the curvature quantity at least) should be apparent from the discussion in Section 5. We found that the canonical invariance of Hamilton's equations implies a coordinate independent metric; hence, the curvature quantity involving derivatives of the metric is zero. This is consistent with the earlier work of H.C. Lee [13, 26, 27], where the curvature quantity for symplectic spaces is defined as (compare with the Riemannian case - (2.18)):

$$K_{ijk} = \partial_i a_{jk} + \partial_j a_{ki} + \partial_k a_{ij}. \quad (7.1)$$

As pointed out in [26], an attractive interpretation appears with the definition of (7.1) and the Poisson bracket expressed (from (5.8)):

$$[w'^k, w'^l]_{PB} = \partial_i w'^k \partial_j w'^l a^{ij}.$$

Considering the cyclic permutation of $[w'^i, [w'^j, w'^k]]_{PB}$, we have

$$[w'^1, [w'^2, w'^3]] + [w'^2, [w'^3, w'^1]] + [w'^3, [w'^1, w'^2]] = K^{ijk} \partial_i w'^1 \partial_j w'^2 \partial_k w'^3, \quad (7.2)$$

where K^{ijk} is the contravariant associate of (7.1) given by $K^{ijk} = a^{il} a^{jm} a^{kn} K_{lmn}$. If the space is flat, then we see that (7.2) satisfies the Jacobi identity:

$$[w'^1, [w'^2, w'^3]] + [w'^2, [w'^3, w'^1]] + [w'^3, [w'^1, w'^2]] = 0, \quad (7.3)$$

so in this case the Poisson bracket defines a Lie algebra - as discussed by many authors (see for example [4, 28, 29]). But the point of interest here is that the Jacobi relation is not satisfied unless the Hamiltonian phase space is flat - implied by the canonical invariance of Hamilton's equations.

Another topic that deserves comment is the traditional use of exterior calculus to describe Hamiltonian invariance, and the Riemannian expression for distance; (2.7) for Hamiltonian phase space. Since we have been referring to a_{ij} as a metric quantity, it seems natural to consider the Riemannian

form: $\Omega^2 = a_{ij} dw^i dw^j$ (see for example Misner, et al [30]), but due to the antisymmetry of a_{ij} we have immediately that $\Omega^2 = 0$; so this expression is not positive definite. In fact, Ω^2 formed in this manner does not give the usual definition of Euclidean distance: $ds^2 = \delta_{ij} dw^i dw^j = dq^2 + dp^2$, used for example in the calculation of the Lyapunov spectra [31] for chaotic systems. The first difficulty may be overcome by allowing the exterior algebra as a defining property of the Hamiltonian space - for then the antisymmetry of the exterior product allows us to obtain a positive definite quantity for $\Omega^2 = a_{ij} dw^i \wedge dw^j \rightarrow$ defining the Hamiltonian space as a symplectic manifold (see Arnold [4]). In fact, the definition of (7.1) follows naturally (although it is only postulated by Lee) using the Generalized Stokes Theorem [32, 33]:

$$\oint_{\partial\Sigma} \Omega^2 = \iint_{\Sigma} d\Omega^2 \Rightarrow \oint w_i \wedge dw^i = \iint dw_i \wedge dw^i \equiv \iint (\partial_k a_{ij}) dw^k \wedge dw^j \wedge dw^i \\ \Rightarrow \partial_i a_{jk} + \partial_j a_{ki} + \partial_k a_{ij} = 0,$$

using exterior differentiation and the permutation of ijk .

The second difficulty mentioned above is not necessarily resolved, but at least seems more reasonable if we simply allow the Hamiltonian theory to possess 2 invariant quantities: ds^2 and Ω^2 - whose preservation in either case gives the Poisson bracket condition for canonical invariance. On the one hand, we may regard δ_{ij} as providing the metric for phase space, and on the other - a_{ij} as the metric for the tangent space to phase space determined from the canonical structure of Hamilton's equations. Considering the case of 2-d phase space, this may be emphasized by writing Hamilton's equations as

$$dw^i = \varepsilon^{ij} \partial_j H dt,$$

and noting that ε^{ij} functions as a raising/lowering metric for the coordinate differentials. The use of δ_{ij} for phase space is consistent with the scalar quantity derived from a vector of \mathbb{C}^2 as illustrated in (6.15).

The corresponding quantities that arise from the unitary form are identified by considering what scalar quantities may be formed from dz^1 and $dz^{\bar{1}}$. The natural choice is apparently (as in (6.15)):

$$dz^1 dz_1 = (dw^1)^2 + (dw^2)^2,$$

which we may express in matrix form as

$$\frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} dz^1 & dz^{\bar{1}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} dz^1 \\ dz^{\bar{1}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7.4)$$

In index form we may write (7.4) as

$$ds^2 = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{i\bar{j}} dz^i dz^{\bar{j}}, \quad (7.5)$$

with $\delta_{i\bar{j}}$ defined as a “hybrid” Kronecker delta with components:

$$\delta_{i\bar{j}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7.6)$$

Note also that we are allowing dz_1 to be raised to $dz^{\bar{2}}$, etc., to obtain the proper components with the summation convention - and we have already obtained ε_{ij} in (4.28). In fact, the Hamiltonian of (5.29) may be expressed in the form of (7.5), but with δ_{ij} in this case given by the direct sum of (7.6) to itself.

Finally, we note that all of these quantities appear when Hamilton’s equations are expressed

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{w}^1 \\ \dot{w}^2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_1 H \\ \partial_2 H \end{pmatrix} = 0,$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \dot{z}^1 \\ \dot{z}^{\bar{1}} \end{pmatrix} + i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial_1 H \\ \partial_{\bar{1}} H \end{pmatrix} = 0,$$

noting that complex conjugation of the 2nd equation has been accounted for using (7.6). To summarize, there are 4 spaces that arise naturally in the study of Hamiltonian dynamics (see figure below): we have phase space with elements, (w^1, w^2) , metric $\delta_{i\bar{j}}$; the tangent space to phase space with basis elements, (dw^1, dw^2) and metric ε^{ij} . The eigenspace of phase space is \mathbb{C}^2 with metric $\delta_{i\bar{j}}$, and the tangent space to \mathbb{C}^2 has the basis elements (dw^1, dw^2) and metric $\varepsilon^{i\bar{j}}$. It is of further interest to note that

when viewed collectively, the metrics we have identified provide a basis for the complex Clifford algebra [34, 35, 36, 37], $Cl(1,-1)$.

The defining relation is given by

$$\sigma_{(i} \sigma_{j)} = g_{ij} I,$$

with

$$\{I, \sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tilde{\sigma}\} \equiv \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}; \quad g_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\tilde{\sigma}$ is given by the antisymmetric combination

$$\tilde{\sigma} = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^{kl} \sigma_k \sigma_l = i \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

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